

Evaluation of performance gains by combining high-density receive arrays with transceiver arrays for brain imaging at 7T

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Synopsis

Motivation: To improve signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) in deep brain structures while using high-density receive arrays at 7T.

Goals: Compare SNR and g-factor performance of conventional transmit-only receive-only arrays with receive arrays combined with transceiver arrays.

Approach: Transceive function was introduced on 8Tx63Rx and 16Tx96Rx 7T head coils, so that the number of receive channels during acquisition increased by 8 and 16, respectively. Three healthy volunteers were scanned, and SNR and g-factor maps were calculated for the different configurations.

Results: The transceiver configuration provided about 16% increase in the central SNR. At higher acceleration factors, especially the 112-channel receive configuration provided improved g-factor performance.

Impact: High-density receive-only arrays provide high SNR close to the surface while maintaining the central SNR under sample noise dominant conditions. Transceiver loops surrounding the receive array enhances the central SNR at 7T, although not as high as reported at 10.5T.

Introduction:

The NexGen 7T scanner at the University of California, Berkeley is the first of its kind equipped with 16-transmit and 128-receive channels and an investigational head gradient coil ('Impulse', Siemens Healthineers, Erlangen Germany) capable of achieving a maximum gradient strength of 200 mT/m and slew rate of 900 T/m/s per axis¹. A 16Tx96Rx array² and an 8Tx63Rx array³ has been developed for this scanner. Recent work on utilising transmit elements during signal reception⁴⁻⁷ has generated interest in this topic because of its potential to enhance the signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) in deep brain regions. In effect the inclusion of transmit elements creates two layers of receiver loops having different size, coverage and at different distances from the brain⁸. This is particularly relevant in high-density receive arrays because increasing the number of receive channels only improves the SNR close to the surface coils⁹. However, the performance gains achieved by combining transceivers with receive-only arrays is dependent on frequency and transceiver array type^{4,5,7}. In this work, we have implemented transceiver function on the two coil arrays presented earlier^{2,3} so that there are 112 and 71-channels, respectively, during signal reception, and SNR and g-factor gains are presented.

Methods:

Coil 1²: The transmit array consisted of sixteen conventional loops arranged in two rows of 8-elements each. The active detuning circuit in the transmit element was disabled and custom-built TR switches were introduced, such that the modified coil has 16-transceiver elements and a total of 112 -receive elements. The phase between the transmit element input and the TR switch was controlled such that

preamp decoupling is achieved when the transceiver element is looking into the low-impedance preamplifier during receive.

Coil 2³: There are 8-transmit loops arranged in a single row. These were converted to transceiver loops as explained in the earlier section, and the modified coil had 8-channels during transmit and 71-channels during receive.

Three healthy volunteers were scanned before and after the transmit coil was modified as a transceiver. SNR measurements were taken using a whole-brain 2D proton-density weighted gradient-echo sequence [TR/TE/flip angle (FA) = 5s/3.82ms/90°, slice = 2 mm, matrix = 256x88, FOV = 256x176 mm², readout bandwidth (BW) = 335 Hz/pixel, TA=7:22 min]. Noise covariance information was acquired using the same pulse sequence without RF excitation. SNR maps were calculated using the noise covariance-weighted optimal coil combination^[10, 11]. FA maps were acquired using a pre-saturation pulse with a turbo-flash readout^[12] [TR/TE/FA = 5s/2.02ms/90°, slice = 1.5 mm, matrix = 256x88, FOV = 256x128 mm², BW = 335 Hz/pixel, Turbo factor = 128]. SNR maps were then normalized by dividing them by sin(FA) to isolate the receive sensitivity. SENSE *g*-factor maps were computed using coil sensitivity maps generated from the fully sampled 2D gradient-echo data [TR/TE/FA = 10ms/4.8ms/15°, slice = 5 mm, matrix = 256x256, FOV = 210x210 mm², BW = 390 Hz/pixel] and measured noise covariance matrices¹³.

Results:

The SNR gained by combining the 96-channel array with 16-channel transceiver is shown in figure 1. Up to 16% gain was measured in the central ROI with no SNR penalty in the periphery. For the 71Rx configuration, the SNR gain, averaged over the three subjects, is 17% and similar SNR was measured in the peripheral ROI. The transceiver configurations also show decreased *g*-factor (increased retained SNR as measured by 1/*g*) at higher acceleration factors, particularly for the 112ch array (figure 3). Marginal improvements in 1/*g* factor values were seen when the 63-channel array was combined with 8-transceiver elements. The *g*-factor performance of both coils alleviates the concern of coupling between the transceiver and the receive array, which could diminish the differences in coil sensitivities. The noise correlation matrix shown in figure 5 demonstrates that preamplifier decoupling implemented on the transceiver elements was sufficient to minimize coupling with the transceiver elements.

Discussion and conclusion:

This work presents for the first time receive performance gains while combining transceiver arrays with 96 and 63-channel arrays for brain imaging at 7T. Such configurations are possible in the NexGen 7T scanner at Berkeley because of its 128-channel receive capability. In conventional scanners, the receive array should be modified such that the total number of receive channels, including the transceiver option, is limited to 64-receive channels (presented separately). While the SNR gain at 7T is not as substantial as achieved with the 10.5T 16TxRx112Rx array⁷, this study demonstrates that it is still possible to achieve gains with conventional transceiver loops instead of employing dipoles which is substantially more complex to combine with high-density receive arrays due to its tuning sensitivity.

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Figure 1: (A) FA normalised SNR maps consisting of 112 receive channels (96 receive-only and 16 transceiver). (B) Corresponding SNR maps of the 96-channel receive array. (C) Percentage difference in SNR demonstrating increase in central SNR while maintaining SNR in the periphery. (D) Box plot quantifying the SNR gain in central and peripheral ROI. (E) The central ROI is highlighted in yellow and the peripheral ROI is shown in red.

Figure 2: A and B are FA normalised SNR maps of the 71 channel (63-receive only and 8 transceiver) array and the 63-channel receive only array. (C) Percentage difference in SNR demonstrating increased SNR away from the surface coils when combined with transceiver array. (D) Average SNR gain calculated from three volunteer data shows similar SNR in the peripheral ROI and about 17% gain in the central ROI.

Figure 3: (A) 1/g factor values for different acceleration factors using the 96-channel array is shown in green, and the combined 112-channel array is shown in red. The 112-channel array consistently performed better than the 96-channel array. (B) Average 1/g factor values calculated from three different healthy volunteer data shows the same trend as shown in (A).

Figure 4: (A) 1/g factor maps comparing the 63Rx and 71Rx arrays. (B) Mean data from the three datasets. While the data shown in figure 3B shows clear gains for the 112-channel array configuration, the g-factor values of the 71Rx configuration remain comparable with the 63Rx data.

Figure 5: Noise correlation matrix of the 112 and 96 channel arrays. The yellow box in figure A corresponds to the 16-transceiver elements, which shows very minimal coupling to other channels.